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The treatment of Marriage in Kavery Nambisan's Mango Colored Fish

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Abstract

A family is the basic unit of any society, where marriage plays a key role. Marriage is the celebration of life. In patriarchy dominated societies, women are not given a free hand to express their opinion in selecting their life partners. As an individual human being, her opinion should be important, but facts remain contrary in a traditional society like India. Kavery Nambisan's *Mango-coloured Fish* (1996) attempts to expose the inner feelings of a young girl, Sharada who is engaged to an eligible bachelor, Goutam. Her pre-marital dilemmas make her explore the real meaning of marriage. In the process, she happens to meet different people, which lead her to a realization of what she wants in her life. This paper attempts to analyze how Nambisan treats marriage and dissects the man-woman relationship within its ambit.

Keywords: Family- marriage- pre-marital dilemma

Introduction

Born in the splendid coffee and spice district of Karnataka, Coorg, in 1947, Kavery Nambisan has emerged as one of the notable writers of Indian English through her significant works such as *The Scent of Pepper*(1997), *On Wings of Butterflies* (2002), *The Story That Must Not Be Told* (2010), and most recent *A town Like Ours* (2014). She embarked on her literary career by contributing to children's magazines, women's magazines, and then proved herself as a successful novelist. With equal intensity, she justifies her profession as a surgeon. Her *Mango Colored Fish* (1996) exerts a feminine argument on marriage, in the backdrop of post-independent modern India.

Literature is a living document that reflects the social, cultural, traditional, and political conditions of that age. Human relationships betwixt the genders and their reaction to the world are the central themes of literary works. Among all the human relationships, the relationship between man and woman has a significant place in currents of life, and the sustainability of this relationship which has been the prime mover of the world stands on the system called 'marriage'. Samuel Johnson in his *Rasselas* (1759) in chapter 26 opines "Marriage has many pains but celibacy has no pleasures", as it has its prominent place in society as well as in binding man-woman relations. In the Indian context, marriage is of primal importance for human social bonding and a mode of socio-cultural regulation which also imposes order onto a society.

Nambisan has a clear opinion on marriage. She protects the serenity of marriage on the one hand and exposes the bondless marriages on the other hand in which we find no fruitfulness.

Many Indian English women novelists like Kamala Markandaya, Anita Nair, Manju Kapoor, Shoba De, Nayantara Sehgal Anita Desai have focused on the man-woman relationship in multifarious forms since women novelists probe into the nuances of the Indian marriage system and also both describe and critique the social institution of marriage.

Mango-Coloured Fish

The female protagonist of *The Mango-Coloured Fish*, Sharada (Shari), born to a typical domineering mother and everything okay father, is attracted to Gautam, an eligible bachelor when she attended a party along with her family members. When he proposed her she finds no reason to reject and then she is engaged to him. But her internal dilemma about marriage initiates her into a journey to know what marriage means. The novel chronicles the exploration of Shari within the traditional norms of marriage and attempts to make an in-depth analysis of the relationship between husband and wife. She feels that her parents are not living for themselves. Their lives are a mere spectacle for others to witness. She has been grown watching the lifeless bond of her father and mother, and so she has no so good impression on marriage. Shari resents her highly domineered, controlled life, dominated by her mother, her too perfect elder sister Chitra and even by her passive father. Hence, she hates it. Marriage, to her, is

an experimental journey, where she seeks to explore the very institution.

At first, she goes to Vrindavan where she stays for few days with her doctor brother Krishna, who is married to Tejaswini (Teji), also a doctor, to have first-hand information about love marriage (since theirs is one). She then goes to Delhi to meet Yashoda (Yash), her childhood friend, who used to receive several love letters when she was at school but has an arranged marriage. Then she stays for a few days in a hostel in Delhi, where she happens to meet a widowed old man, George who lives with the memories of his lost wife. She also witnesses the life of her mother's half-sister Paru aunt and uncle, though fascinated by their mutual relation but later realizes that there exists a relational gap between them too!

At Vrindavan, when Shari is with her brother Krishna to understand his married life, she attempts to gauge their happiness. They both work at a hospital, not for any profits, but purely to serve humanity. She finds them dedicated to their profession. When she asks him the reason for having clashed with their mother, he answers thus: "Mother goes on about us not having children. There is plenty of time. **It is not children, not sex, family adjustments or job success, it is that two people are happy together**" (MCF 66) (emphasis mine). With this reply from her brother, she understands that there are many other things in married life and not just children. Shari observes the relationship between Krishna and Teji only to get clarity about what marriage is, and to some extent she achieved it. In the words of Zai Whitaker in an article "Road to Self-Discovery" on *Mango-Coloured Fish* opines, "Krishna

and Teji are high-minded doctors who serve in a small rural clinic. Theirs is a committed and evolving relationship, one of argument and discussion, sulking, and reconciliation of active hearing and being heard" (43). Teji tries to make Shari understand that love alone would not suffice and that intentions must be pure, promises are to be kept and commitments are to be made to make a success of any marriage. She says, "Marriage is a mirage because people choose to see only the icing on the cake" (MCF 56). She also explains her that there will be many instances where the husband and the wife should understand each other and to go further not to the opposite directions but to one direction which leads to a world of bliss. She further says about how relationships occur, "Every person longs to meet another all the way. Even DNA is a double-stranded molecule, pair-bonded with its mate. The best relationships improve with time" (MCF 56). Being with Teji and Krishna, Shari's confusion on marriage has been cleared to some extent.

Later she moves to Delhi where Shari gains the opportunity to understand the real plight of Yash. Though hers is a seemingly portrait-perfect arranged marriage, she is not truly happy, though she pretends to be so. She is sick of her family life. For her, adultery is a vile and a daily humiliation, but for her husband Satya, it is normative. Yash is aggrieved: "I'm sick, sick, sick of it. Adultery is vile, for me, it's a daily humiliation...and my kids when I tell them: be good, be honest, my mouth hurts" (MCF 121). The purity and sustainability of man-woman relations are based on mutual respect and love whether it is a love or arranged marriage.

Nambisan has clear spectra about marriage. She writes, "...arranged marriages seem to work better than the so-called love marriages. Just because two people decide without outside opinion that they are suited to each other, it doesn't mean they're in love. They may be guided by other considerations like money and social standing" (MCF122). The novelist illustrates this with example. For instance, a college graduate from a wealthy background falls in love with a college graduate from an equally wealthy background; the daughter of an IAS officer chooses to marry an acquaintance who has his car and whose father owns a thriving. She is little inclined to marry the son of a school teacher who rides a bicycle. "Love, dear girl, is very *matlabi* most of the time. You should see the west, where every marriage is a "love" marriage. The way the women and men chase each other is enough to make you sick" (MCF 122). Amulya Malladi, a well-known Indian English writer in her novel *Serving Crazy with Curry* (2004) expresses a similar opinion that arranged marriages are the only option for the young generation. She opines that when there is a discourse of true marriage, certainly there will be mutual maturity and understanding between husband and wife.

Yash clearly states to Shari that it is not love that makes the world go, around but it is hunger. As Shari's Paro uncle says, no two marriages are the same. The premarital dilemmas which Shari expresses are almost equal to that of Bharat's in *The Truth (Almost) About Bharat*. He is also in a state of confusion in understanding his parents who are always quarrelsome. When Shari looks at

the life of her Paro aunt and uncle, she thinks that marriage is like a sweet bond unlike the bond between her parents. The endearing and unending saga of the love story between her Aunt and Uncle allows her to unravel the dilemma of her marriage to Gautam.

Shari has been very keen to understand marriage and tries in many ways to realize the reality in the man-woman relationship in a marriage. Even when she is at a coffee house or at a restaurant, she tries to understand the couples who come across by carefully observing their behavior. In one such instance, she watches a couple but remains unable to understand the intensity of their relation, as they don't exchange at least a word throughout their stay. Finally, she concludes that they are either bitterly unhappy or so well matched that their only reason for coming to a restaurant is to eat and nothing else.

During her brief period of staying in a hostel in Delhi to explore her 'self', Shari meets George, a widowed old man, and realizes his deep attachment with his wife. His company in the hostel makes her to understand how a husband can be a true friend and lover who can love his wife with equal intensity even after her death. His life can be compared with Simon, the protagonist of *The Story Must Not Be Told*, who is also a widowed old man, living with the memories of his wife. Shari feels as if "growing and stretching towards something" for which she has come to find and gradually realizes what she needs. (MCF165)

The relation between a man and a woman can be strengthened only if the need, warmth and love are mutual. This

is true in the relation of Naren and Shari. Naren, a blind and working as a teacher, is a friend to her with whom she has long talks and walks. They feel comfortable to be in each other's presence. For Shari, the physical disability of Naren is not at all a problem of making a relation with him. Their intimacy becomes closer due to their compatible wavelength and thought. Like her, he also teaches, and he hopes to achieve something by being a teacher. He too wants to be self-confident and self-empowered, and more than, that he passionately aims at ushering in a social change, which fascinates Shari.

During her stay at Delhi, Shari goes to the University hostel where Naren stays, to meet him without giving him prior intimation. When she doesn't find him there, she is disappointed. She felt that if he were here, she would talk, fight, argue and be friends. "When I was with Naren, my mind moved and swayed in unpredictable ways. How we scuffled! Tapping and teasing, teasing, teasing and tearing, and nibbling and scrunching into each other's minds, like two puppies jostling in the mud. Sometimes, we would think the same thought and it was like sipping through one straw" (MCF 99). This above expression of her reveals that she is not physically attracted to him as she is attracted to her fiancée, Gautam. She experiences a kind of higher love for Naren. She checks herself that any relationship based on merely physical attraction cannot be sustained long. Hence he rechecks her decision of marrying Gautam.

Shari's psychological struggle in taking an important decision in her life has got a solution when she compares her fiancé Gautam and her friend Naren. While leaving for Delhi, she told him that

she would often call him but his reply, "How much can you say when you know the money's trickling away?" (MCF 33) He also asks her to arrange some foreign exchange by taking the advantage of her friends who are living in England. This kind of expressions of Gautam gives her an opportunity to understand his psychology that he is giving weight to money than her. She wants to be a teacher but Gautam wants her to do an M.B.A which would be useful when he sets up a company of his own and she doesn't want to live up to "someone's expectations" (MCF 37). In a letter to Naren she has written that she is in love with somebody, and to Gautam she has written, "I love you, my dearest", but now she realizes the fact that it is a lie, and she is lying to herself. "The Lie written in a letter - growing bigger all the time" (MCF 85). Finally, Shari refrains from marrying Gautam as she realizes what she exactly wants; she, at any cost, doesn't want to be "moulded" and at anymore (MCF 73). She can be compared to Miriam of Margaret Atwood's *The Edible Woman* (1969) who also has a similar feeling that her fiancé Peter is metaphorically devouring her.

Conclusion

Nambisan makes her readers realize the true meaning of marriage. Initially, though Shari was fascinated by physical appearance and status of Gautam, and later with whom she is engaged, as a result of her journey she discerns that she cannot find the true essence of marriage with him, "I can feel myself leaping out of the cage I have prisoned myself in, I savour the joy of being me. Where is the sense of living by somebody's rules?" (MCF 240) Instead of taking a peripheral decision at the crucial

junction of her life, she takes a pause to listen to her heart. It is a pause which costs the cancellation of her engagement with Gautam, a pause that makes her to understand her needs, a pause that ignites her to come out of the cuckooed life. According to Nambisan, marriage should not be a mechanical relationship of convenience, but it is more than that. She has a vision of the interdependency of man and woman, and marriage is such a platform where the both should feel equality in all corners of their life and it must not be a monotonous. Human relations can be sustained only through the right understanding and positive attitude, and the relationship between a wife and a husband is not exception to it.

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